

Wnt6 signalling in *Xenopus laevis* eye development

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Abstract

The eyes are the most important sensory organs for most vertebrates. Their structure and development is conserved between several vertebrate species. The development is regulated by several signalling pathways, including the Wnt/ β -catenin signalling pathway. It is required for several aspects of retinal development and it is known to regulate the proliferation of neuro-epithelial stem cells.

In *Xenopus laevis* the intracellular Wnt/ β -catenin signalling pathway is activated in the retina by the Wnt receptor Fz5. Fz5 function in the eye was shown to regulate tissue specific gene expression and neuron versus Müller glia differentiation. However no candidate Wnt ligand that could act through the Fz5 receptor in this tissue had been described.

Wnt6 was found to be expressed in the developing retina, indicating that Wnt6 and Fz5 share temporal and spatial expression. We show that a knock down of Wnt6 led to the same phenotype seen in Fz5 morphants, including reduced eye size, changed marker gene expression and altered neuron/Müller glia ratio. Rescue experiments show that the observed phenotype is specific and is mediated by altered Wnt/ β -catenin signalling pathway function. These results make Wnt6 a candidate for Fz5 ligand.

Introduction

The eye is a sensory organ sensible to information from light. It consists of several cell types with only two neuronal cell types required for light detection. The functions of the other neuronal cells are mainly transmitting the electrical signal from the photoreceptors to the brain. The non-neuronal cells within in the retina are called Müller glia and have supporting and degrading functions. These cell types origin from one stem cell type which proliferation and differentiation is highly regulated during retinal development. One key player of this regulation is Wnt/ β -catenin signalling, also known as canonical Wnt-signalling.

Wnts are lipid-modified proteins which resemble in structure a “hand” and an “index finger” Janda *et al.* (2012). The C-terminal (the “index finger”) end is essential for signal transduction. Different Wnt proteins are synthesised and secreted by different cell types within the animal (Cadigan and Nusse, 1997). In the Wnt/ β -catenin signalling the Wnt molecule binds to a Frizzled (Fz)-receptor and a LRP5/6 co-receptor. It plays a central role during various stages of retinal development as establishing the retinal field, neuronal specification, or development of cornea and lens (Lad *et al.*, 2009).

During the development of the eye several Wnt proteins are synthesised and secreted. There is also a various number of Fz receptors expressed during this process (Van Raay and Vetter, 2004). In chicken 11 Wnt genes are expressed in the anterior part of the eye in a distinct spatial and temporal pattern (Fokina and Frolova, 2006) suggesting that signalling has different functions during eye development. Using TCF/Lef-Lac-Z reporter gene to mark cells where TCF/Lef-transcription factors are activated by canonical Wnt/ β -catenin signalling, Liu *et al.* (2006) observed activation of canonical Wnt/ β -catenin signalling in the ciliary marginal zone (CMZ), the neuroblast layer of the developing retina, and in an apical pattern in the outer neuroblast layer, a region

containing differentiating photoreceptors. This indicates that canonical Wnt/ β -catenin signalling is required for the differentiation of neural cells in the retina. The differentiation of neural retinal precursor (NRP) cells follows an established order in cell-fate determination with exit from the cell cycle, while Müller glia cells are the last cell differentiating from the progenitors. In medaka canonical Wnt/ β -catenin Wnt signalling regulates cell cycle progression, proliferation, apoptosis and differentiation of NRP cells (Sanchez-Sanchez *et al.*, 2010).

The Fz receptors Fz3 and Fz5 and Fz7 were found to be expressed in the eye (Rasmussen *et al.*, 2001; Sumanas and Ekker, 2001; Wheeler and Hoppler, 1999). Fz3 induces ectopic eye development and perturbs endogenous eye development when overexpressed. In mouse activates with Wnt11 the PCP signalling pathway (Yamanaka and Nishida, 2007) and functions in angiogenesis (Stefater *et al.*, 2011). Fz 5 is only expressed in the developing retina in *Xenopus* (Sumanas and Ekker, 2001). Van Raay *et al.* (2005) used transgenic embryos carrying a reporter transgene (TOP:dGFP) consisting of four consensus TCF/Lef binding sites coupled to a basal *c-fos* promoter driving the expression of destabilized GFP to show that Fz5 activates the canonical Wnt/ β -catenin signalling pathway in *Xenopus* retina. They also showed that Wnt signalling via Fz5 plays an important role during proliferation of neurons. The expressions of *sox2* and *ash3b* are reduced in the retina of Fz5 morphants while it is unaffected in other part of the CNS. Sox2 and Ash3b function as markers for a neuronal fate of the cell. Van Raay *et al.* (2005) described that there was an increase of Müller glial cells in Fz5 morphants and the amount of neural cells was decreased all neuronal cells compared to untreated embryos. They interpreted that changed neuron/Müller glia ratio as a consequence of reduced neuron differentiation during retinal development. They did not observe any increasing rate of apoptosis in Fz5 morphants, what they took as another indicator for their hypothesis that Fz5 plays a role in the differentiation of neurons in the retina. It shares this function with Fz8 in mural retinal development (Liu *et al.*, 2012).

In *Xenopus laevis* activates the canonical Wnt signalling pathway (Lavery *et al.*, 2008d). In chick Wnt6 is a pan-epidermal marker. It labels the entire surface from the anterior part to tail levels (Schubert *et al.*, 2002). By HH18 its expression spreads laterally from the di/mesencephalic neural fold to label the epidermis lateral to the brain and dorsal to the branchial arches. Between HH15 and HH18, this staining intensifies around the eye. It also labels the otic vesicle. Lavery *et al.* (2008a) showed that Wnt6 is also expressed in overlaying surfaces in *Xenopus laevis*. Its expression reaches a peak at stage 28 when multiple organs start to form. At stage 18 to 19 it is expressed throughout the ectoderm but is upregulated in the dorsal tissues of the neural fold. By stage 23 it is expressed in the eye and head region, the pronephric anlagen, the somites and the skin. At stage 43 Wnt6 RNA expression is seen in the rod outer segment of the retina but not in the lens itself. This indicates that it functions within the retina.

Wnt6 and Fz5 share a temporal and spatial expression in *Xenopus laevis*. We will show that a knock down of Wnt6 has a similar effect as knock down of Fz5. So we assume that Wnt6 is a possible ligand for Fz5.

Results

Knock down of Wnt6 has an effect on eye development

Wnt6/ β -catenin signalling is required for retinal development. It was shown that a knock down of this signalling pathway leads to reduced eye size (Van Raay *et al.*, 2005). Lavery *et al.* (2008a) showed that Wnt6 is widely expressed during embryonic

development in *Xenopus laevis*. One region where it is expressed in is the CNS and overlaying epithelium. This lead to the assumption that it also function in its development. Wnt6MO2, Wnt6MO3 or controlMO was injected into the left dorsal blastomere. The phenotype of these embryos was analysed at stage 41. The controlMO was used to be sure that any observed phenotype is not an artefact caused by the injection itself. Uninjected embryos were used as second control. Three different phenotypes were observed in Wnt6MO injected embryos: normal developed eyes, reduced eye size or missing eyes. Embryos showing one of these phenotypes were counted (Fig. 1). In uninjected embryos 1.25% (n=1/80) showed the phenotype of a reduced eye size and in none the eye was missing. All injected embryos showed an increase of reduced eye size and missing eyes but there were differences. In embryos injected with controlMO 11.1% (n=8/72) showed reduced eye size and the eye was missing in 1.39% (n=1/72) of the embryos. But the uninjected embryos and the embryos injected with controlMO are statistically similar (p=0.01). The change in embryos injected with Wnt6MO3 was significant (p<0.001). In 45.9% (n=39/85) of these embryos eye size was reduced and 23.5% (n=20/85) embryos were missing the eye on the injected side.

Wnt6MO2 was injected to analyse any off target effects of Wnt6MO3. These off target effects were phenotypes seen in Wnt6MO3 morphants but not in Wnt6MO2 morphants. No off target effects were observed but more embryos (52.5%; n=21/40) showed a normal eye phenotype compared to Wnt6MO3 injected embryos (30.6%; n=26/85). Already Lavery *et al.* (2008d) described a higher efficiency of Wnt6MO3 compared to Wnt6MO2. Also we observed a toxic effect of Wnt6MO2 leading to a much lower survival rate. The assumption is that Wnt6MO2 was less effective in the survivors. For these reasons I focussed on using Wnt6MO3 for any further experiments.

These data suggest that Wnt6 is required in eye development. Van Raay *et al.* (2005) observed a similar effect in Fz5 knock down embryos. They had found that it is due to a changed neural marker expression. For this reason we investigated if the knock down of Wnt6 has any effect on the expression of *sox2* and *rx1*.

Effect on *sox2* and *rx1* expression in after Wnt6 knock down

The reduced eye size could be caused by effects on different stages of eye development, Rx1 is required for initial initiation of retinal development and their subsequent proliferation. An early knock down in *Xenopus laevis* results in micro- or anophthalmia. (Bailey *et al.*, 2004). The expression of *sox2* was chosen to investigate if the amount of neural stem cells had changed in Wnt6 knock down embryos. In mice the removal of Sox2 causes the complete loss of neural progenitor competence in divide and differentiate (Taranova *et al.*, 2006). The expression of these two markers were investigated at stages 15 and 25. At stage 15 the eye field is established but it is not divided into both eyes. At stage 25 neurogenesis is taking place. In any case it would give us an idea when the Wnt6 is required.

At stage 15 *rx1* expression is not affected. As well in injected embryos and in uninjected control embryos the expression did not change. But a significant difference (p<0.001) in *sox2* expression. There was a reduction of its expression in Wnt6MO3 injected embryos. 87.5% (n=7/8) showed normal *sox2* expression but it was reduced in n=1/7. (Fig. 2) This could indicate that the eye field developed normally in Wnt6 morphants but neurulation could be affected. Therefore a stage-specific inhibition of Wnt6 function was done and the expression of *sox2* was analyzed at stage 25. (Fig. 3) We used a dnWnt6. Its function was tested investigating its ability to inhibit the development of a second body axis. Ventrally injected Wnt6 mRNA can induce the development of a

second body axis. If a co-injection of Wnt6 mRNA and dnWnt6 mRNA shows a reduced amount of embryos with a second body axis, it can be assumed that dnWnt6 inhibits Wnt6 function. Neither uninjected control embryos nor embryos injected only with cmVGF mRNA developed a second body axis. 41.82% (n=69/165) of Wnt6 mRNA injected embryos had a second body axis. The number was significantly ($p < 0.001$) reduced in co-injected embryos (4.83%, n=13/269) (supplementary data S1).

Fig. 3 shows that the expression of *sox2* in dnWnt6 positive transgenic embryos is significantly affected ($p < 0.001$) compared to non-transgenic embryos. 79.3% (n=23/29) non-transgenic embryos showed normal *sox2* expression but only 11.1% (2/18) transgenic embryos. On the other hand in 55.6% (n=10/18) of transgenic embryos *sox2* expression was missing. Also the proportion of embryos with reduced *sox2* expression was increased in transgenic embryos (33.3%, n=6/18) compared to non-transgenic embryos (6.9%, n=2/29). In embryos missing *sox2* expression in the developing eyes still show this expression in the developing telencephalon (Fig. 3C asterisk) where Wnt/ β -catenin signaling is inhibited. It proves that WMISH worked also in these embryos and the effect is genuine.

These data indicate that Wnt6 has an early function in retinal development. Since we saw an early effect on *sox2* expression in Wnt6 morphants it cannot be excluded that even at Wnt6 functions indirectly during retinal development. It could affect one of these early stages what affects neurulation during later stages. To test if Wnt6 also functions later we used a stage-specific rescue experiment. We used the drug BIO to induce β -catenin signaling after stage 17 by inhibiting GSK3 function. The used control was MeBIO. It has a similar structure as BIO but is not able to inhibit GSK3 function. The uninjected control MO and embryos injected with Wnt6MO3 or control MO were incubated in 1 μ M BIO in 0.1xMMR until stage 27. The embryos for WMISH were fixed at stage 25 but some were left for later analysis to check if the morpholino and BIO had worked on these embryos. Fig. 4 shows the expression pattern of *rx1* and *sox2*. A variation of *rx1* expression between the different experiments could be seen; even in uninjected control embryos. *rx1* expression seems to be reduced in Wnt6MO3 injected embryos compared to uninjected embryos. But this difference is not significant ($p = 0.299$). The other observed differences are not significant too.

As at stage 15 the expression of *sox2* was affected at stage 25. All uninjected and non-treated embryos showed normal *sox2* expression. 31% (n=9/29) of uninjected BIO-treated embryos showed increased *sox2* expression but also 13.9% (n=4/29) showed reduced *sox2* expression. The difference is significant ($p < 0.001$). *sox2* expression was reduced in 66.7% (n=12/18) of Wnt6MO3 injected embryos and missing in 16.7% (n=3/18) of these embryos. This difference is significant compared to uninjected and untreated control embryos ($p < 0.001$).

For another rescue experiment the morphants were co-injected with β -cateninGR mRNA (Afouda *et al.*, 2008). This form of β -catenin can be experimentally activated by Dexamethasone. We got similar results as after activating β -catenin signaling by BIO. (SUPPLEMENTARY DATA S2). But the results were not significant but showed a trend similar to the results caused by BIO. This could be due to light degradation of the mRNA or better incorporation and function of BIO.

The reduced expression of *sox2* and that it was rescued by experimental induction of β -catenin signaling are indicators that Wnt6 is required during retinal neurulation.

Cellular effect of Wnt6 knock down

Sox2 plays an important role during fate decision of retinal neuronal stem cells (Agathocleous *et al.*, 2009). It was shown that a reduced *sox2* expression increases the amount of Müller glia in favor of Müller glia. Embryos from the batches used for

analysis of *sox2* expression in morphants and BIO treated embryos were allowed to develop until stage 41. CRALBP is specific for Müller glia. Acetylated tubulin is a protein in cilia and their derivatives. Therefore it can be used for staining the axons of neurons (shown by Li *et al.* (2010)). The amount of neurons and the amount of Müller glial cells was counted. In the next step the number of neurons was divided by the number of Müller glia. Fig. 5 shows that in uninjected and untreated embryos had a ratio of about 2.1 (n=8). That number was hardly affected by BIO and MeBIO treatment. The seen difference is not significant ($p=0.352$). A similar ratio is seen in embryos injected with control embryos (ratio: 1.8). It was reduced in Wnt6MO3 injected embryos to a ratio of 1.6. The difference is statistically significant ($p<0.001$). After treating the Wnt6MO3 injected embryos with BIO the neuron/Müller glia ratio was restored to a value similar to uninjected control embryos (ratio: 2.1, n=8, $p=0.948$). The difference between untreated and BIO treated Wnt6 morphants was only slightly significant ($p=0.095$).

This analysis was also done for embryos injected with β -cateninGR mRNA. These embryos showed a similar ratio as the BIO treated embryos (SUPPLEMENTARY DATA S3). But the observed differences were not as significant as in BIO treated embryos but the same trend is to be seen.

The changed neuron/Müller glia ratio in Wnt6 morphants are another indicator that Wnt6 functions during retinal neurulation.

Possible interaction of Wnt6 and Fz5

As we showed Wnt6 functions in eye development. It seems to regulate proliferation and differentiation of retinal neural stem cells. A reduction of Wnt6 leads to an increased amount of Müller glia. A similar phenotype was described by Van Raay *et al.* (2005). They showed that a reduced Fz5 function affects the neuron/Müller glia ratio with an increased amount of Müller glia. This was caused by a reduced *sox2* expression in Fz5 knock down embryos. Because of these similarities we hypothesized that Wnt6 and Fz5 would interact in regulation of proliferation and differentiation of retina neural stem cells and the Fz5 ligand is not yet known.

First it was analyzed if Fz5 affects Wnt6 functional activity. Wnt6 activates the β -catenin signaling pathway. Therefore we injected 60 μ g of Wnt6 mRNA with 100 μ g Fz5 mRNA. Exogenous Wnt6 can induce axis duplication. The assumption is that the co-injection increases the amount of embryos showing a second body axis. As control cmVGFP mRNA was injected. The second control was an injection of 100 μ g Fz5 mRNA. It has to be done to exclude the possibility that Fz5 can form dimers and activate β -catenin signaling. It was shown for Fz1, Fz2 and Fz3 but not for Fz7 (Carron *et al.*, 2003; van Gijn *et al.*, 2001). Fz5 alone was not able to induce second axis formation but the co-injection of Wnt6 mRNA and Fz5 mRNA increased the number of embryos with second body axis formation significantly ($p=0.006$) compared to embryos only injected with Wnt6 mRNA (SUPPLEMENTAL DATA S4).

Secondly the effect of dnFz5 on Wnt6 overexpression on *sox2* during retinal development expression was analyzed. Wnt6 DNA was co-lipofected with dnFz5 DNA. The idea behind it is that dnFz5 would bind the surplus Wnt6 and normalize *sox2* expression. The function of this method was shown by Lhomond *et al.* (2012). 41.7% (n=5/12) of Wnt6 lipofected embryos displayed an increase in *sox2* expression. The difference between Wnt6 lipofected embryos and cmVGFP lipofected embryos was significant ($p=0.007$). *sox2* expression was decreased in 31.3% (n=3/16) of dnFz5 lipofected embryos (Fig. 6, Van Raay *et al.* (2005)). The difference to cmVGFP lipofected embryos was significant ($p=0.015$). (Fig. 6)

Fig. 6 also shows that dnFz5 modifies the effect of Wnt6 overexpression. None of the embryos lipofected with Wnt6/dnFz5 showed increased *sox2* expression. In 9.1% (n=1/11) *sox2* expression was missing and in 18.2% (n=2/11) of these embryos *sox2* expression was reduced. Most embryos showed normal *sox2* expression (72.2%; n=8/11). They are similar to Wnt6 overexpressing embryos (p=0.084) but more similar to dnFz5 lipofected embryos (p=0.495). They are also similar to cmVGF lipofected embryos (p=0.152). So, the *sox2* expression in Wnt6/dnFz5 lipofected embryos rather resembles the expression of *sox2* of dnFz5 lipofected embryos.

Both experiments indicate that Wnt6 and Fz5 can interact during eye development in *Xenopus laevis*. So, Wnt6 is a probable ligand for Fz5 during retinal proliferation and differentiation.

Discussion

For most animals the eye is the most important sensory organ. In vertebrates it derives from precursor cells from the diencephalon. The proliferation and differentiation of these cells are strictly regulated. Several signalling pathways play a crucial role in this regulation. It was shown that the Wnt/ β -catenin signalling pathway is one of them regulating the proliferation of retinal stem cells (Agathocleous *et al.*, 2009). But several members of the Wnt protein family are expressed in the developing eye (Van Raay and Vetter, 2004) and Wnt6 is one of them (Lavery *et al.*, 2008a). The different Wnt proteins were identified as regulators in self-renewal and stem cell maintenance or differentiation (Lad *et al.*, 2009). It was also implied that Wnt signalling control cell cycle in some regions of the CNS, through control of the cell cycle machinery (Megason and McMahon, 2002). The function of Wnt6 was not known. In this paper we showed that an inhibition of Wnt6 function leads to reduced eye size proving that it plays a role during early eye development. In Wnt6 inhibited embryos the expression of *sox2* is reduced while the expression of *rx1* is hardly affected. The effect on *rx1* seen in Wnt6 morphants could be due to the already reduced eye size, because it was never missing as *sox2* was. Because *rx1* expression was not affected in the eye field (stage 15) we could conclude that Wnt6 functions during retinal proliferation and differentiation. We also analysed *pax6* expression in stage 15 and 25 and it was hardly affected as well (Data not shown).

The shown reduced expression of *sox2* indicates that the proliferation of retinal stem cells could be affected. *Ash3b* is required for neurulation but its function depends on the induced cell fate of the progenitor (Turner and Weintraub, 1994). A WMISH for *ash3b* expression was performed but its expression is generally weak and so it was often difficult to detect. But what we could see indicated that *ash3b* expression is reduced in Wnt6 morphants (data not shown). Both the reduced *sox2* expression and the reduced *ash3b* expression are indicators that the differentiation of retinal stem cells into neurons was disturbed. As we showed that ratio between neurons and Müller glia was changed. The amount of Müller glia seemed to be increased.

A similar phenotype was described in Fz5 morphants (Van Raay *et al.*, 2005). We took this similarity to hypothesize that Wnt6 functions via Fz5 in retinal neuronal development. We showed that they can functionally interact by analysis of embryos co-injected with Wnt6 and Fz5. But we did not show that it affects Wnt target genes directly. We repeated the experiment by Medina *et al.* (2000). The Wnt6/Fz5 mRNA solution was co-injected at stage 3. At stage 7 animal caps were taken and allowed to develop until stage 17. We analysed the expression of *siamois* using qPCR. But the *siamois* amount we got was too low for proper analysis. But it showed a trend indicating that the described effects are genuine.

It still has to be considered that Fz5 is not the only Fz receptor functioning during retinal development. We found functional similarities of Wnt6 and Fz5 which could be indirectly. We showed that Wnt6 and Fz5 can functional interact. But it is still no evidence that they interact during retinal development. More experiments proving this assumption would be necessary.

Materials and Methods

Xenopus laevis embryo manipulation

Following ethical standards oocytes were harvested and used for in vitro-fertilization. For phenotype analysis Wnt6MO2 and Wnt6MO3 antisense oligonucleotide morpholino (MO) (Lavery *et al.*, 2008d) were injected in a total concentration of 40 ng/cell into the left dorsal blastomere at stage 3.

Whole mount in situ hybridisation (WMISH)

The embryos were fixed in MEMFA at room temperature for 1 hour. They were washed in an increasing methanol (MetOH) series and stored in MetOH at -20°C. The DIG-labelled probes for *sox2* (Kishi *et al.*, 2000), *pax6* (Hirsch and Harris, 1997) and *rx1* (Zuber *et al.*, 2003) were synthesized using the Ambion Megascript kit. During the first day the embryos were washed in a decreasing MetOH series at room temperature (RT). They were bleached in 5% formamide+0.5xSSC+1%H₂O₂ at RT for a short moment. Then they were fixed in 4%PFA. After they were washed in PBT they were washed with 0.1M triethanolamine and then twice in 0.1M triethanolamine+0.25% acetic anhydride. Before they were incubated in the hybridisation buffer the embryos were washed in PBT. The hybridisation was performed at 65°C over night. The embryos were washed in a decreasing formamide/SSC solution at 65°C for 30 min. Then they were washed 2x in MAB at room temperature for 5 min. The incubation of the -DIG antibody was done at 4°C over night (o/n). The embryos were washed in MABT solution at room temperature for 30 min. For the staining reaction a 1:3 dilution of BM-Purple (Roche) was used.

Cryosections and immunofluorescence staining

Embryos were fixed in Dent's fixative (20% DMSO in methanol) and stored at -20°C for at least o/n. Embryos were rehydrated by placing them through a series of washes with decreasing methanol and increasing PBS+0.1%Tween (PBST) (5 min/wash). The last wash was done in dH₂O. Embryos were equilibrated in tissue tech (LAB TAAB from Sigma) for 1 hour then frozen at -40°C and stored at -20°C overnight. Tissue was sectioned at a thickness of 12 µm and mounted onto polylysine coated slides. They were washed in warm dH₂O and allowed to dry at room temperature. The slide were washed 3x in PBS/5% BSA at room temperature for 5 min. Then the slices were washed in PBS/0.1% Triton-X 100 at room temperature for 20 min. Afterwards they were washed in PBS/5% BSA for 5 min. Then they were blocked in PBS/5% BSA/10% normal donkey serum for at least 1 hour at RT. The -CRALBP antibody (gift from J. Saari University of Washington, Seattle; Bunt-Milam and Saari (1983)) was diluted 1:1000 in blocking solution. The neurons were stained using a mouse -acetylated tubulin (Sigma) diluted 1:1000. The sections were covered by VectaShield containing DAPI (Vector Labs).

Transgenesis and heat shock treatment

Transgenic tadpoles were generated by the method described by (Amaya and Kroll, 1996). For isolation of sperm nuclei 10 mg/ml digitonin instead of lysolecithin was used

(Huang *et al.*, 1999). The plasmids were linearized using NotI and gel purified with glass milk. After the transplantation of the sperm nuclei the embryos were kept at 14°C until they reached stage 3. The embryos were scanned for polyspermic and unfertilized embryos which were sorted out. The other embryos were put into 0.1xMMR+gentamycin (2000:1) and kept at 14°C until stage 17.

To activate the expression of the transgene a heat shock treatment was done. Therefore the embryos were transferred to 0.1XMMR with a temperature of 34°C. That treatment took 15 min. Then they were transferred back to 14°C. It was repeated four times.

At stage 25 the embryos were scanned for GFP positive ones, because these embryos were transgenic. These embryos and some of the GFP negative embryos were fixed in MEMFA at 4°C o/n. The GFP negative embryos were used as control.

Lipofection

The used method was described by Ohnuma *et al.* (2002). The pCS2+Wnt-6 Full length (mp1) (Hoppler lab), pCMVnGFP (Amaya and Kroll, 1996) and pCS2+dnFz5 (Van Raay *et al.*, 2005) plasmids were mixed 1:3 with DOTAP (Roche). 10 µl of the DNA/transfectamine solution were injected 5 to 8 times into the embryo at stage 17. The injection was done into the optic vesicle.

At stage 32 GFP positive embryos were fixed in MEMFA at 4°C o/n.

Design of dnWnt6

dnWnt6 was designed by a nested PCR reaction. The used primers introduced a stop codon after the aa sequence SPDF to remove the last 71 aa from the C-terminus of the Wnt6 protein following the design pioneered by Hoppler *et al.* (1996). Following primers were used: XWnt6-deltaC-nested-F 5'-3': GATCTCCATAACGAGGCTG and XWnt6-deltaC-R 5'-3': TCGGTGACGGAGCCTGCATCC The reaction was done by a PFX platinum Taq polymerase and an enhancer. This sample was diluted 1:5 and following primers were added to the dilution: XWnt6- C-F 5'-3': (NcoI site) CATGCCATGGTCTCTCGGGTTCCTGCAC and XWnt6 C-R: CGTAGGGGTCTAAAAACGACTTGATCAG (SpeI site). The band of 200+ base pairs was run on a gel and purified. It was cloned into a pGEM vector plasmid and later subcloned into a pC2+ vector and into a pC2+ HS HSGFP4 vector. It was subcloned behind the first HS promoter.

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Figure 1: Wnt6 knock down affects the development of the eye.

The Wnt6MO was injected into the left side (L) of the developing embryo. Two different Wnt6MO were used. Both type of morphants showed the same phenotype: The eye size was reduced compared to the uninjected control embryo (B) or the uninjected side of the morphant (C right side of the embryo) or embryos injected with controlMO (D). The bar chart in A summarizes the result seen in B and C.

Fig. 2: expression pattern of rx1 and sox2 at stage 15

Figure 3: stage-specific inhibition of Wnt6 function reduces *sox2* expression in the optic vesicle

Wnt6 function was inhibited using a dnWnt6 that was activated at stage 17 by heat shock induction.

- The chart shows that the expression of *sox2* reduced significantly in TG:HSdnWnt6HSGFP embryos at stage 25. The expression only remained in the telencephalon (C).
- Non-transgenic stage 25 embryo what was generated and treated as the transgenic embryos were. It shows normal *sox2* expression.

A Expression of *rx1* in BIO treated embryos

E Expression of *sox2* in BIO treated embryos

Fig.4: *sox2* expression is affected by Wnt6 knock down and reactivation of Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathway

A-D") *rx1* expression in Wnt6MO injected embryos and control embryos appears normal in Wnt6 morphants, uninjected control embryos and embryos injected with controlMO. Neither the inhibition of Wnt6 signalling nor the induction of the Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathway have any effect on the expression of *rx1*.

E-H") reduction of Wnt6 function and induction of Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathway affects *sox2* expression. H) the graph indicates that the reduction of Wnt6 reduces the expression of *sox2* in the developing eye (F'). This expression can be rescued by activation of the Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathway using BIO (G'). This effect was not to be seen by using MeBIO (F'). *sox2* expression was not affected by any other treatment tested in this experiment.

A

Fig. 5: the knock down of Wnt6 affects the differentiation of neurons and Müller glia in retinal development

Neurons were stained with an α -acetylated tubulin AB (B) and Müller glia with an α -CRALBP -AB (C). D shows a merged picture of B and C. The two different type of cells were counted and the number of neurons divided by the number of Müller glia. (A) The graph shows that in untreated and uninjected embryos or embryos injected with control MO about 2 of 3 cells were neurons. In embryos injected with Wnt6 MO3 and being untreated or treated with MeBio this ration (2:1) is changed in favor of Müller glia (1.5:1). Wnt6 morphants treated with BIO developed the normal ratio of neurons to Müller glia.

A

sox2 expression after dnFz5/Wnt6 lipofection

Fig. 6: indication that Wnt6 and Fz5 can interact in the developing *Xenopus laevis* embryo

The bar chart in A shows that *sox2* expression is increased in embryos lipofected with Wnt6 plasmids (D, arrow). The expression is reduced in dnFz5 lipofected embryos (E). The expression of *sox2* was slightly increased in Wnt6/dnFz5 co-lipofected embryos (F) but the Wnt6 mediated overexpression of *sox2* was gone in the analyzed embryos.

S1: test of dnWnt6 functionality

- A) Bar chart shows that the injection of 20 pg Wnt6 mRNA into the prospective ventral mesoderm causes axis duplication. A co-injection of 20 pg Wnt6 mRNA and 500 pg dnWnt6 mRNA reduces the amount of embryos showing axis duplication. dnWnt6 does not induce axis duplication.
- B) Uninjected control embryo.
- C) Embryo injected with 500 pg dnWnt6 mRNA and 20 pg GFP mRNA
- D) Embryo injected with 20 pg Wnt6 mRNA and 20 pg GFP mRNA. The two body axes can clearly be seen.
- E) Embryo co-injected with 20 pg Wnt6 mRNA and 500 pg dnWnt6 mRNA. dnWnt6 inhibited the induction of axis duplication.

S2: 5.3: *sox2* expression after DEX treatment of β -cateninGR injected embryos

L stands for "left side" which is the injected side. The left side is defined by its orientation along the anterior/posterior axis. The dotted line indicates the midline of the embryo.

A) the bar chart shows that *sox2* expression is reduced in embryos injected with Wnt6MO3+ β -cateninGR mRNA. The expression could not be rescued by DEX treatment in embryos only injected with Wnt6MO3 but in embryos co-injected with Wnt6MO3+ β -cateninGR mRNA. The graph also shows that in some embryos an overexpression of *sox2* was to be seen in embryos injected with β -cateninGR mRNA

and treated with DEX. The reduction of *sox2* expression is in a reduced expression domain and reduced intensity.

- B) and B') uninjected control embryos. The embryo in B' was treated with DEX. Both pictures show embryos with normal *sox2* expression.
- C) and C') embryos injected with controlMO. The embryo in C' was treated with DEX. Both picture show embryos with normal *sox2* expression.
- D) and D') embryos injected with Wnt6MO3. The embryo in D' was treated with DEX. Both pictures show embryos with reduced *sox2* expression on in the injected side (arrow). D' show that the reduced expression could not be rescued by the DEX treatment (arrow).
- E) and E') embryos co-injected with Wnt6MO3 and β -cateninGR mRNA. The expression of *sox2* is reduced in embryos not treated with DEX (E, arrow). In the embryo treated with DEX (E') shows that the expression of *sox2* was rescued by experimental activation of Wnt signalling (arrow).
- F) and F') embryos injected with β -cateninGR mRNA. The embryo in F' was treated with DEX. Both pictures show embryos with normal *sox2* expression.

S3: ratio of neurons/Müller glia in embryos injected with β -cateninGR mRNA

red: acetylated tubulin (neurons); green: CRALBP (Müller glia)

- A) Bar chart indicating a trend that experimental induction of β -catenin activity can rescue the ratio between neurons and Müller glial cells.
- B) Neurons stained for acetylated tubulin in a retina of a DEX-untreated uninjected control embryo
- C) Müller glia cells stained for CRALBP in a retina of a DEX-untreated uninjected control embryo
- D) Merged picture of neurons (B) and Müller glia (C) in a DEX-untreated uninjected control embryo

S4: analysis of synergistic effect of Wnt6 mRNA and Fz5 mRNA co-injection

- A. bar chart indicating that Wnt6 mRNA+Fz5 mRNA co-injection increases the effect of Wnt6 mRNA injection. More embryos showed partial or complete axis duplication compared when Wnt6 mRNA was injected alone.
- B. uninjected control embryo showing only one body axis
- C. Wnt6 mRNA injected embryo. At the left side of the embryo a second body axis is to be seen.
- D. Fz5 mRNA injected embryo. This embryo as all other Fz5 mRNA injected embryos did not develop a second body axis.
- E. Wnt6 mRNA+Fz5 mRNA injected embryo. This embryo shows a second body axis on its left side.
- F. Wnt6 mRNA+Fz5 mRNA injected embryo showing partial duplication. The arrow points to a malformation what could be a truncation of a second body axis. Embryos showing this were generally counted as embryos with partial second body axis (also for Wnt6 mRNA injected embryos).

